

Flood inundation analysis based on SAR image and DEM: A case study of the 2021 Zhengzhou Flood in China

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Abstract—In recent years, flood disasters have become more frequent all over the world. It is of great importance to analyze flood disasters by remote sensing image and topographic data. Space-based synthetic aperture radar (SAR) is a powerful tool for monitoring flood conditions over large areas without the influence of clouds and daylight, but it cannot reflect the cause and trend of flood formation. The combination of terrain data and remote sensing data has potential utility in mapping and analyzing large-scale surface floods caused by heavy rainfall. Taking the flood disaster in Zhengzhou, China in 2021 as an example, this paper attempts to analyze the topographic and hydrological characteristics based on the Gaofen-3 (GF3) SAR image and FABDEM data, so as to understand the trend of flood inundation. The experiment demonstrates that combining digital elevation model (DEM) data can facilitate mutual validation of remote sensing image flood monitoring and analysis of urban water flow mechanisms.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to climate change and urbanization, natural disasters are occurring more frequently and affecting more people. A report published in 2020 by the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) confirms that extreme weather events will dominate the disaster landscape of the 21st century [1]. Between 2000 and 2018, the world experienced 913 major flood disasters [2]. How to realize pre-disaster warning and post-disaster rapid detection of floods is very important.

An accurate mapping of the disaster situation can be achieved by extracting flooded areas, and the results combined with pre disaster geographic data can be used to evaluate the post-disaster damage losses.

Flood disasters are often widespread and associated with cloudy weather. Synthetic aperture radar (SAR) is one of the most effective tools for flood emergency monitoring due to its all-day, all-weather earth observation capability. And SAR is very sensitive to surface roughness and other characteristics, so it has high accuracy to extract water extent and to obtain flood range by comparing changes between water bodies before and after disasters.

The most basic water extraction method is image classification. Sui et al. adopted multi-scale level set segmentation and OTSU thresholding method to realize automatic water extraction of SAR image, effectively improving the detection accuracy of flood inundation area [3]. In addition, because the electromagnetic waves generated by the radar are reflected from the water by the mirror, the water body has low brightness in SAR images. This is reversed in forested areas, where the electromagnetic waves emitted by the radar are reflected off the water surface and hit tree trunks and canopies, increasing the backscatter strength.

Flooding is a complex process involving meteorological precipitation, hydrology, topography and other factors. Although the remote sensing image has the characteristics of large coverage and fast data collection in flood disaster monitoring, the development of flood is closely related to topography and

geomorphic information, while the remote sensing image only focuses on surface distribution characteristics.

It is very important to utilize the topographic and geomorphic features for flood hazard risk assessment. By using DEMs to analyze hydrological features and hydrodynamic model, flood simulation can be realized to evaluate the possibility of flood disaster [4]. Compared with only relying on remote sensing image to obtain water distribution information, DEM and other data fusion methods can effectively improve the accuracy of large-scale water identification. Li et al. effectively combined DEM, Landsat, MODIS and water occurrence data to observe surface water changes with finer spatial-temporal resolution [5].

This paper combines SAR and DEM data to analyses the distribution of flood water bodies, and taking the flood disaster in Zhengzhou, China in 2021 as an example. We use the flood area extracted from the Gaofen-3 (GF3) SAR images and the hydrological features extracted from the FABDEM to try to analyses the distribution of the flood inundation.

II. METHODS

The study area is located in Zhengzhou City, Henan Province, China. Most of this area is in the plain, the Yellow River is in the north of the Zhengzhou city, and the southwest corner of the city is a high mountain (Figure 1). On 20 July 2021, Zhengzhou experienced severe flooding due to several days of heavy precipitation. The long-term rainfall weather caused the optical images to be severely obscured by clouds. Therefore, China's disaster reduction department urgently programmed GF3 satellite to obtain the time-series SAR images of the affected areas in time.

The GF3 satellite is a multi-modal imaging SAR sensor, launched in 2016, with single-polarization, dual-polarization and full-polarization modes. The GF3 data used in this paper are dual-polarization (FSII mode) images on July 24, 2021, HV polarization channels, and the spatial resolution is 10m. Image segmentation [3] is used to extract the water range of SAR images, and the results are shown in Figure 2. The GF3 SAR image was used to extract the pre-disaster and post-disaster water body areas in the study area, and the flood distribution areas could be identified through comparative analysis.

Multi-temporal SAR images can be used to monitor the flood range, but there are some errors in the extraction results of urban water bodies, because they are interfered by SAR image noise, and the distribution of surface water caused by rainfall cannot be analyzed only depending on the flood extent.

In order to analyze the topographic and hydrological features of the study area, the river network and basin features were extracted using FABDEM DEM data [6]. This data is a global map of elevation with buildings and forests removed at 1 arc second grid spacing. The hydrological analysis module of ArcGIS software was adopted for the hydrological characteristics.

The distribution of water network and watershed is obtained by calculating the flow direction and flow accumulation data of the study area. Then, the hydrological characteristics and inundation range are combined to analyze the flood distribution.

Figure 1. Location map of the study area in Henan Province, China.

Figure 2. Water extraction results of GF3 image.

Figure 3. Flood distribution map of the study area.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the way of post-classification comparison, multi-temporal SAR was used to extract the flood range, as shown in Figure 3. The blue area is the distribution range of water before the disaster, and the red area is the flood water bodies on July 24, 2021. There are more flood water bodies on both sides of the Yellow River, and the width of the river surface increases significantly due to the flood. A large area of flood water bodies has appeared in the north-east of Zhengzhou. Flood water bodies are also widely distributed around the Zhengzhou city, showing that urban waterlogging is very serious.

Figure 4 is the DEM elevation map of the study area. The terrain of the study area slopes gradually from southwest to northeast, and flooding occurs on both sides of rivers in the southwest region. A large area of flooding and waterlogging occurred in urban areas with relatively flat terrain, and water on urban roads is shown as a linear red area in the image. The city of Zhengzhou, which is located in the plain area, experienced a large area of urban waterlogging after heavy rainfall.

Based on the 30m resolution DEM data of the study area, the river distribution obtained from the flow direction and flow accumulation is shown in Figure 5. Light blue is calculated to get the distribution of the river network in the study area, the dark blue area is permanent water and the red area is flood water. It can be seen that the surface stream in the study area mainly originates from the mountainous areas in the southwest and west of the city, and most of the rivers flow into the southeast of the low terrain after passing through the city.

Figure 4. The elevation of the study area.

Figure 5. River networks and drainage basins in the study area.

Most of the flood water flows to the southeast of the study area after the rainfall, which is consistent with the remote sensing detection results, and most of the flood water is distributed in the eastern part of the city. By extracting the drainage basin of the study area (Figure 5), it can be seen that the flood extent is concentrated in the drainage basin mainly in the urban plain. The eastern part of the city is dominated by agricultural land and these areas have experienced extensive flooding. The combination of geomorphic data and flood data can be used to preliminarily analyze the development state of the flood after the

rainfall, which is of practical value in understanding the development of the flood disaster.

Figure 6. Typical geographic element in the study area

In 2006 researchers conducted a project to predict surface water pooling under different rainfall in Edmonton, Canada. In this work, the urban elevation is modeled with high precision, and the urban surface water pooling under different rainfall conditions is simulated very well based on the hydrology corrected DEM [7]. The report divides flood flow in urban environments into two mechanisms: one is when river water overflows from river channels and accumulates in low-lying areas, and the other is when surface water accumulates in low-lying areas from upland area.

In order to analyze the mechanisms of water flow in the study area, we combined flood inundation data and urban geographic data (such as buildings, green space, rivers, etc.) to analyze the location relationship between the inundation area and surrounding geographic elements (Fig.6). It can be found that the inundation in the study area is mainly caused by surface water pooling in low-lying areas (Figure 6.B), and the inundation area caused by river overflow is mainly distributed in the southwest area of the city (Figure 6.A).

However, there are still some problems to be solved in the evolution process of urban waterlogging based on remote sensing images and DEM data. Due to the complexity of the surface of urban areas, SAR image cannot meet the requirements of fine extraction of urban inundation area. In addition, the combination of remote sensing images and topographic data has not been able to achieve a more objective and automated analysis of urban area flooding mechanism.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, SAR image and DEM data are used to analyze the geomorphic features of the flood inundation area in Zhengzhou, Henan, China in 2021. The results show that heavy rainfall causes severe waterlogging in the urban areas and tends to flow southeast of the city. In the future, it is necessary to use topographic data with higher resolution remote sensing images to realize more accurate analysis of urban flood inundation.

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